

Preparing the ground for a commercial exploitation of TRICK

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Our main findings

The traceability tool market has seen rapid growth due to rising demand for **transparency, efficiency, and sustainability** from companies across different sectors. The primary challenge of the deliverable 6.4 was to find a scalable path for positioning the output of TRICK in a highly competitive market and prepare the research output for the commercial scale-up.

The analysis reported in the following paragraphs aims at demonstrating that TRICK traceability tool has several unique selling points that distinguish it from competitors, including the **coexistence of advanced technologies like Blockchain and AI** and the **readiness to the digital product passport data model**: a digital dossier attesting the lifecycle of products and components that is expected to be mandatory in the coming years. By aligning its development with market needs and addressing customer priorities, TRICK is positioned to capture significant market share as the supply chain traceability sector grows over the next decade.

The TRICK platform has proven to be a valuable solution for addressing the key needs of modern supply chains, particularly in terms of **sustainability, ethical sourcing, and transparency**. The results of a survey conducted with the project consortium suggest that there is significant market demand for TRICK's services, with high willingness to pay, especially for features that focus on **compliance, counterfeiting prevention, and environmental responsibility**. By targeting key stakeholders such as IT providers, certification bodies, and public institutions, TRICK is well-positioned to capitalize on the growing need for reliable and scalable traceability solutions.

A brief overview of the traceability tools market

The challenge in the deliverable 6.4 was about finding a common path among project partners to scale-up and position TRICK's key exploitable results in a competitive market as that of traceability tools.

In 2024, the market of the supply chain traceability experienced a rapid growth, fueled by a rising need for transparency, efficiency and sustainability by companies of all industries and sizes.

In the coming years, from 2024 to 2030, the global supply chain traceability market is expected to grow further at a compound annual growth rate of 15-20%. Currently, this market is valued for more than \$15 billion, with projections that it will exceed \$50 billion by 2030.

For a new service to succeed in this profitable market segment is paramount to focus on the adopters needs and catch the unexplored market frontiers, by mastering the cutting-edge technologies such as **Blockchain, Internet of Things (IoT), AI e Machine Learning**.

Being Trick an EU research project gathering the expertise of various partners with a wide experience in IT, research and commerce (public administrations, private companies, universities and research bodies), it blossomed from a solid ground of knowledge. Moreover, the iterative tests with the pilots and the learnings absorbed throughout the project enabled further adjustments and improvements to prepare it for a future commercial strategy.

Understanding the value proposition of TRICK against competitors

As in every product development procedure, understanding its value and market positioning is crucial to define a successful product strategy that drives real business outcomes.

This task usually involves different preliminary steps such as the comparison with similar services, the understanding of the needs of target users, the evaluation of possible improvements based on a risk assessment and, finally, the choice of the suitable long-term scaling strategy.

In TRICK scale up, setting the market position against competitors was a preparatory activity to a more in-depth analysis of customer needs. The competitors were selected according to their outreach and offering ranging from manufacturing, beauty and wellness, fashion to food, operating within and outside the EU.

The comparative analysis highlighted common aspects (points of parity) and distinctive features (points of difference) of TRICK compared to the potential competitors. The distinctive features of TRICK representing a potential commercial advantage were found to be as follows:

- **PEF (Product Environmental footprint):** Unlike many companies, where carbon footprint assessment relies upon general national standards, TRICK supports “PEF”

(Product Environmental footprint), that is considered to be valid internationally and ensures stricter LCA (life cycle assessment) calculations.

- **Blockchain and AI in one product:** TRICK system shows the strategic coexistence of two cutting edge technologies for the value chain traceability: Blockchain and AI. This synergy ensures an accurate and reliable verification of the production flow at each step. The tracking facilities that are usually provided by different services can be achieved by using a single service thanks to TRICK versatility
- **Food platform and predictive shelf-life simulation:** The shelf-life simulation tool provided for the TRICK food version is a powerful ally against food waste. This additional service provides customers with useful insights to recycle food at the end of its shelf cycle (e.g. by processing it through juices, jams and other complex food products)
- **Readiness to the DPP (Digital Product Passport) data model:** is a digital record that provides detailed information about a product's lifecycle, enhancing the traceability throughout the supply chain. Supporting the DPP among the services can result in a highly competitive advantage for a company helping in complying with regulations and enhancing their market position by building trust
- **Data portability:** The data portability has been observed as being a TRICK feature that is often absent among other competitors. It refers to the ability of the software to integrate input data from external sources and to produce output data ready to be used by other stakeholder of a value chain. TRICK has proven to technically fulfil this requirement although it is not mature enough to be adopted as a standard. For that reason, its improvement should be considered among the staples of the commercial development of TRICK

Once the aspects that make TRICK a highly competitive solution were outlined, it was time to gather actionable insights from the consortium partners to capture the needs of their average users. The inspected metrics were:

- The willingness to pay
- The business needs that would be addressed by each feature of TRICK
- The additional adaptations in which to invest in to launch TRICK in the market
- The prioritization level of each of the proposed adaptation in term of urgency

Given the high number of attendants, this goal was achieved by designing a lean process. The inquiry model was that of the survey in order to collect concise and easily processable data. The following paragraph summarizes the enquiry results.

The advantages of TRICK from customers' point of view

The analysis of the survey results summoned the insights of consortium partners about the key exploitable results of TRICK. It also gave an effective understanding of the expected appreciation of customers about transparency and ethical assessment.

The metrics tested during the survey, namely the willingness to pay and the correspondence between the enabled services and user needs revealed an encouraging scenario and tested the relevance of the key exploitable results from a commercial point of view, given the state of the art.

In order to fully understand the benefits brought about by TRICK, it is useful to identify its potential adopters (as shown in dlV in D8.4 Strategic Plan Final Version) and trace a correspondence with the survey results. The following list shows an overview of the principal customers around the traceability business:

- IT providers for large clothing brands
- Component suppliers
- Recycling hubs
- Certification providers
- Banks and financial institutions
- Players in the logistic segment
- Customs agencies
- Public institutions and decision makers

The actors listed above share a common interest in the adoption of reliable and solid traceability services as those enabled by the key exploitable results of TRICK. Consumers and authority are increasingly concerned about the sustainability and ethic of the supply practices. Companies seek traceability solution able to ensure responsible sourcing practices to reduce the environmental impact and improving social awareness. These details justify the high “willingness to pay” registered during the survey for the following TRICK features:

- **Traceability service**
- **Preferential Certificate of Origin**
- **AI for counterfeiting**
- **Blockchain related services**

As stated before, the TRICK research project allowed partners to continuously improve and test the solution, turning the output into a complex and thorough solution which integrates the most innovative and useful traceability services in one platform.

As far as users' needs are concerned, the services offered by TRICK have proven to satisfy the major business needs of the players operating in the manufacturing landscape:

- Environmental and ethic-related needs:** the survey participants highlighted the importance of **Transparency and sustainability throughout the supply chain**. The increasing urgency of a change in the production approach due to the environmental impact of production and processing of raw material (especially in the textile industry) is indisputable. Innovative leaders are trying to shift their production methods to a more responsible model.
- Brand reputation and positioning-related needs:** the adoption of a structured traceability service allows adopters to be considered by potential customers as responsible and innovative. This perception fuels the Competitive advantage and the **Company reputation building and consolidation**.
- Compliance-related needs:** governments around the world are increasing the regulatory requirements related to traceability, with a particular concern the food and pharmaceutical industries. The adoption of TRICK allows customers to stay up-to-date with legal requirements on the one hand, and enjoy tax reliefs on the other. Sometimes companies process raw materials coming from other suppliers. TRICK's implementation of **AI for counterfeiting fights smuggling and other illegal habits**.
- Costs-related needs:** by integrating TRICK in the production process, companies and institutions can take advantage of **Financial benefits** deriving from the Preferential Certificate of Origin: a document attesting that goods in a particular shipment are of a certain origin under the definitions of a particular bilateral or multilateral free trade agreement.

Figure 1: The partners rating of the benefits enabled by the Traceability service of TRICK

Solutions based on blockchain, IoT and AI are coveted by SMEs and large companies. The demand for blockchain-based traceability services in enterprise supply chains is expected to grow rapidly in the coming years. Blockchain technology, known for its ability to provide transparency, security, immutability and data traceability, is increasingly being used by companies to streamline their operations and improve supply chain management. The sector

that reveals the greatest interest for traceability-based services are: food, fashion and luxury, logistics and transports and the pharmaceutical one.

Possible scaling strategies for TRICK

Once core values and purposes are identified, a suitable scale up strategy must be pursued to improve the offer.

Horizontal scaling

This method consists in widening the offer. In TRICK it could be achieved by:

- Introducing new add-ons or services beside the existing ones
- Finding new geographical areas to expand the outreach of the product
- Tailoring the existing services to the needs of unexplored industries

Vertical scaling

Unlike the horizontal scaling, the vertical one focuses on developing and empowering the existing services. In the case of Trick, the vertical scaling could consist in:

- Improving the already existing features
- Adopting new technologies or updates to make the existing ones even more effective
- Choosing a certain market segment or business in which to specialize

Diversification

This scale-up strategy differs from the previous one. Unlike the horizontal and Vertical scaling, diversification refers to the development of new services in addition to current offering, to rely on different products types.

In the context of TRICK, this could be done by adding new products that cater for different user needs. This diversification can involve expanding into market segment that are similar to the previous one (related diversification) or entering entire new businesses (Unrelated diversification)

Recommendations for scaling up

The final part of the inquiry conducted in the deliverable 6.4 called the attention on certain aspects concerning the scale up of TRICK's key exploitable results, and to the prioritization level of each improvement.

The development of a powerful and articulated tool involves a number of adaptations and arrangements which are essential to facilitate its adoption by customers and ensure an

effective user experience. The survey highlighted the following recommendations to take into account from a business perspective:

- **Graphic Restyling:** Graphic restyling is crucial in the commercial development of a product because it enhances its visual appeal, aligns it with current design trends, and strengthens brand identity. A well-executed restyling can make a product more attractive to consumers, improve its market perception, and increase its relevance in a competitive landscape. It can also refresh a brand's image, visually communicating the innovation, which can boost consumer confidence and drive sales.
- **Communication and Marketing:** Communication and marketing are essential to the commercial development of a product because they create awareness, build consumer interest, and drive demand. Effective communication ensures that the product's value, features, and benefits are clearly conveyed to the target audience, while strategic marketing helps position the product in the market, differentiate it from competitors, and attract the right customers. Together, they shape consumer perception, foster brand loyalty, and ultimately contribute to increased sales and market growth.
- **Customer Support Infrastructures:** Customer support infrastructures play a crucial role in the commercial development of a product by enhancing customer satisfaction, loyalty, and overall experience. A strong support system ensures that issues are resolved quickly, helping to maintain positive customer relationships and reduce churn. As customer feedback is gathered and acted upon, it can provide valuable insights for product improvements and innovation. Effective customer support also builds trust and credibility, making customers more likely to recommend the product, leading to increased sales and long-term business growth. In short, robust support infrastructure is vital for sustaining product success and fostering a positive brand reputation.